

INFORMATION BEHAVIOR RESEARCH

INTRODUCTION

The term "information behavior" refers to the most currently employed terminology to describe the various, diverse ways human beings engage themselves with information. Specifically, it focuses on the varied methods and approaches individuals take toward searching for and using information in their everyday living. Information behavior is a term that is very well known in the discipline of library and information science. It is specifically a subdiscipline that is dedicated to engaging in an extensive variety of types of research. The research is conducted with the primary aim of gaining a deeper understanding of the multifaceted human relationship to information. The growing interest in this particular area has developed as a result of multiple streams of thought and inquiry that intersect and influence one another. Librarians were interested in learning more about the behaviors and needs of library users, for the better service of their patrons. Government agencies wanted to know how scientists and engineers used technical information, specifically what they accessed and how; their aim was to speed the introduction of new research findings and developments. Social scientists, as a general class, were interested in understanding the various social uses and consequences of information in different contexts and scenarios. In the more recent past, the social studies of information technology, including the developing field of social informatics, have made great contributions to our understanding in this important area of study. In library and information science, there are several types of streams of research used exclusively to gain a deeper understanding about the behavior of information more qualitatively and substantially. Information research behavior specifically involves unique patterns and strategies individuals follow when engaging in seeking, gathering, evaluating, and eventually using information in given contexts. This is an area of study key in the fields of information science, library studies, psychology, and human-computer interaction and can vary in scope based on the context, goals, and tools used.

HISTORY OF INFORMATION BEHAVIOR RESEARCH

1. Early Foundations Pre-1950s

Information behavior as a distinct field of study has early history not formally recorded. But if looked at the development of the concept of libraries and the evolution of information retrieval systems, roots can be traced to a long time ago. Scholarly and professional workers during the early 20th century, like Paul Otlet and Henri La Fontaine, developed foundational concepts related to organizing and classifying information. They created the Universal Decimal Classification system. Library science during this time was more about cataloging and organizing information than studying the human behavior in relation to information use.

2. The Emergence of Information Retrieval: 1950s-1960s

Information retrieval (IR) became the dominant paradigm in the 1950s and 1960s,

supported by technological innovations such as the invention of computers and the emergence of databases. The emphasis was on enhancing search systems so that it could retrieve the relevant documents based on user queries.

Information-seeking behavior is an area of study that surfaced from the increasing interest in the ways people interact with such systems. Research has generally focused on the cognitive aspects of searching, such as how users come up with queries, refine them, and assess the relevance of the information.

The work of Marcia Bates, particularly her studies on "berry-picking" behavior in information-seeking, was pivotal in shifting the focus from formal models of IR to more human-centered studies of information use.

3. Cognitive and Psychological Approaches (1970s-1980s)

The 1970s and 1980s saw a significant shift toward understanding the cognitive processes underlying information behavior. Researchers began examining information-seeking behavior from psychological and cognitive perspectives, studying how users navigate complex information environments.

Herbert Simon and other thinkers, in addition to their ideas, contributed to decision-making, problem-solving, and cognitive psychology, influencing the research regarding how individuals seek, process, and use information.

Kuhlthau's Information Search Process model in 1991 has become the standard in describing the phases of information-seeking behavior, mainly in academic and research contexts. The model stresses emotional and cognitive experiences users experience when they interact with an information system.

4. Human-Centered and Social Approaches (1990s-2000s)

This developed further in the 1990s to include broader social and contextual factors that influence information behavior, including cultural, organizational, and social influences. Researchers started to consider the influence of social networks, community contexts, and cultural factors on information seeking and sharing.

The term information behavior itself evolved into a more comprehensive term than traditional information retrieval; it included all forms of information activities—seeking, acquiring, using, sharing, and managing.

It explored beyond individual information behavior, examining group and organizational sharing and even how groups and organizations share information as people cooperate in sharing it and what system designers need to do in creating these information systems.

Influencers in this time frame are Dervin's theory of sense-making for information behavior and Bates, continuing on the concept of information seeking.

5. Digital Information and Technology (2000s-Present)

The rapid advancement of digital technologies and the widespread use of the internet significantly transformed information behavior. Researchers began exploring how digital environments (search engines, social media, digital libraries) influence how people seek, access, and use information.

New information behaviors appeared with the emergence of social media and other web-based services, like content sharing, crowdsourcing, and participatory information behaviors. Diffusion and the way knowledge spreads within online

communities were of utmost importance to research.

Information behavior studies have become increasingly interdisciplinary and cross-disciplinary, based on human-computer interaction (HCI), cognitive science, library and information science, communication studies, and sociology.

Big data and machine learning also reshaped the information behavior study, especially towards understanding how people interact with personalized content and information recommendation systems.

INFORMATION SEARCHING VERSUS INFORMATION SEEKING

This discussion focused research on how people relate to information, how and when they find it, and to what uses they put it to. But it needs to be appreciated that across all this time a complementary corpus of research and practical engagement was underway that attended the details of the activity of searching itself. That is, in working with paper and online resources, many problems were encountered and skills needed to succeed in the specific acts associated with locating information in a paper or online resource. Bates' articles on information-searching tactics and search techniques[85,86] promoted greater attention to the complexities of identifying sources and working one's way through resources to locate the desired information. A series of research followed that considered both search success and desirable design features of information systems to enhance ease of use[87–91] (See also ELIS entry "Information searching and search models."). Even browsing, generally considered the most non-structured approach to information searching, was not left untouched

ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN INFORMATION BEHAVIOR RESEARCH

1. Data Collection and Analysis

Digital Platforms and Tools: Technology allows researchers to collect data from a vast array of digital platforms, including social media, search engines, databases, and websites. Digital tools like web scraping, API integrations, and user behavior tracking software help researchers understand how people interact with information online.

Big Data Analytics: Information behaviour researchers can now examine extremely large amounts of data due to big data; machine learning, sentiment analysis and predictive analytics are employed for identifying trends in information-seeking behavior at scale.

Real-time Monitoring: Technology can support real-time tracking of information seeking behavior. This helps researchers study how users act instantly, that includes search queries, clicks and also other forms of interaction with the digital content.

2. New Information Seeking Techniques

Search Engines and AI: the discovery of information has changed a great deal with the introduction of search engines, especially those utilizing AI and machine learning. Knowing how users interact with such technologies—how they form queries, modify the searches, and evaluate results—is a central issue for studies in information behavior.

Recommendation Systems: The fact that recommendation algorithms are so widely used (e.g., on YouTube, Netflix, or Amazon) gives an idea of how algorithms affect information behavior, what people watch, read, or buy.

Voice Assistants and Chatbots: Virtual assistants like Siri, Alexa, and Google Assistant have changed the way people seek information. The research now focuses on the subtleties of voice-based information retrieval and the human-computer interaction involved.

3. Changes in Information Use and Sharing

Social Media and Information Sharing: The social media space (for example, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram) is critical for analyzing how people share, appraise, and consume information. It is also changing collective information behavior through the spreading of misinformation or how to create and curate content.

Crowdsourcing and Collective Intelligence: Technologies that enable crowdsourcing, such as Wikipedia and Reddit, allow researchers to study collaborative knowledge production and how collective intelligence emerges through user interactions and contributions.

Mobile Technology and Accessibility: With mobile devices, users are accessing information in more varied contexts, such as on the go, and in micro-moments. Information behavior research is exploring the impact of mobile accessibility on how, when, and where people seek and use information.

4. New Frameworks and Theories

Digital Literacy: Technology's role in shaping the way people interact with digital information has led to the development of new frameworks around digital literacy. This includes understanding how individuals assess the credibility of online information and navigate digital environments safely.

Information Overload: The increase in information availability through technology has also prompted research into information overload. How users cope with excessive information and manage to make decisions or retain useful knowledge is a key focus area.

Context-Aware Information Systems: Advances in context-aware computing, where systems respond to users' location, activity, or personal preferences, have introduced new ways to study how context influences information behavior.

5. Improved User-Centered Design

Human-Computer Interaction (HCI): The study in HCI is based on understanding how users interact with technology and how interfaces may be designed to support

effective information retrieval. It thus drives the development of more intuitive search interfaces, tools, and systems that align with the cognitive processes of human beings.

Personalized Information Systems: With advances in AI and machine learning, it is possible to create personalized information systems that learn and adapt based on individual users' preferences, behaviors, and past interactions. There is emerging interest in understanding how personalization impacts information-seeking behaviors.

6. Ethical and Privacy Concerns

Data Privacy: As reliance on technology for information gathering increases, issues regarding user privacy, data security, and consent are at the center of information behavior research. Researchers are investigating how users perceive and manage privacy risks in interactions with information systems.

Bias in Algorithms: As technology increasingly mediates information access and behavior, the potential for algorithmic bias—where certain information is favored or suppressed—has emerged as a crucial research topic. Information behavior researchers are investigating how biases in search results or recommendation systems affect users' information environments.

7. Interdisciplinary Approaches

Information behavior research has been facilitated by the interdisciplinary nature of technology through computer science, psychology, sociology, communication studies, and cognitive science. An interdisciplinary approach allows for an integrated understanding of how technology affects the way people behave when interacting with and processing information.

Topics in information behavior research

What do we know about seeking information? It's hard to summarize briefly, but the topics of research that continue to evolve reveal our growing understanding of the human relationship with information. Here's a brief sample: Information Behavior India—In the 1940s and 1950s, information seeking focused on literature—books, journals, handbooks—and institutions. It examined book circulation, reference questions, and public library usage by different economic strata. In the 1960s and beyond, studies of information seeking and use by the general public opened out the research to incorporate many sources of information. The first surprise was to discover how much information—in both personal and professional contexts—people got from friends and colleagues. In a study examining how scientists learned of things by accident, Menzel found out that other scientists were immensely significant in that process. In truth, in a significant amount of studies, human preferences to get information from other people were well supported. The "principle of least effort" has always proved to be the best in human information seeking. While it appears obvious that people prefer the least amount of effort, research has shown that easy access and use outweigh information quality. Due in particular to one's often unjust belief he may filter good information from a flow of faulty sources, persons very

characteristically undersearch for really reliable information. Information seeking behavior is usually unself-conscious; that is, problems are typically solved without selfconsciously thinking about obtaining required information. Information seeking behavior is seldom differentiated from general problem-solving behavior. Effective research design in information seeking must recognise that asking people what they have been doing recently usually leads to low internal validity. Dervin has always underscored this insight. For a prime example of her research technique, see Dervin. Thus, as a rule, people—even including Ph.D. scholars—develop what search skills they have incidentally to their primary efforts at research or problemsolving and often fail to develop a conscious repertoire of search skills and techniques to help them over difficult stages. Many college students feel intense discomfort with library research; this has been the focus of several studies, which has come to be known as "library anxiety" (see ELIS entry "Library anxiety"). There is a great body of literature on teaching "information literacy," the ability to seek and evaluate information (see ELIS entries "Information literacy" and "Information literacy instruction"). Briefly, many do not tap resources as optimally as they might—and do so inefficiently. It was only in the 1960s that the focus on the culture of science made it possible to discuss information seeking across academic disciplines in more nuanced ways from the 1970s onwards. Patrick Wilson talks about "cognitive authority," Julie Hurd deals with information use patterns in library design .Paisley focuses on "information and work," Robert Taylor looks at "information use environments," Cronin examines invisible colleges (informal researcher groups), Leckie et al. model professional information seeking, and Budd and Bates contrast science and humanities cultures. In the underresearched area of archival resources, Barbara Orbach and Wendy Duff and Catherine Johnson have given good descriptions of the use of historical archival materials. During the 1980s and 1990s, several researchers deepened the understanding of various aspects of information behavior by exploring questions and areas previously not as well understood. Elfreda Chatman examined the information environments of janitors, women in a retirement home, and prisoners.. Cheryl Metoyer-Duran applied the concept of gatekeeping to five minority groups in Southern California and developed sophisticated—and sometimes counterintuitive—understandings about information flow within minority communities, and between them and the larger society. 128. The challenge of studying unconventional groups and domains even extended to abused women¹²⁹ and abused children.¹³⁰ Carol Kuhlthau is another researcher who has had very wide influence in the information behavior world. She developed and refined a model of student information seeking based on multiple studies demonstrating research skills. Her model runs counter to many assumptions in both education and library and information science about how people tackle researching a paper or project, and how that experience can be substantially improved over past approaches. Specifically, she discovered that the combined process of researching and writing a paper is complex and difficult for most people—indeed, the library research is inextricably bound with the understanding and gradual formulation of the thesis of the paper. The concept of "choosing a topic" like picking an apple and researching it in the library is a far cry from how this process should play out. But many educators have sent students off unprepared for this crucial exercise in writing a paper. Empirically-grounded model of daily activities relating to scholarly information seeking developed by David Ellis, a number of follow-up

studies have been motivated to find similar activities in the other's work of 2080 Information Behavior India—Information Behavior other settings. And, of course, Brenda Dervin's sensemaking as a motivation for information seeking formed the underlying model for much information behavior research.⁶⁰ In the 1990s and 2000s, along with the growth of the ISIC community, researchers widened their view of information behavior to take into account the whole environment—physical, social, and technological—in the study of how people interact with information. Social context and social situation were identified as fundamental to the understanding of information seeking. Karen Fisher (nee Pettigrew) developed the concept of "information grounds"—the joint creation of social environments by people in which to share conversation and information. Disciplinary examples of these rich analyses include science and business. As pointed out above, the study of "information practice," as a shaping paradigm for information behavior research, has emerged strongly in the twenty-first century.[83] Several recent studies have demonstrated particularly creative approaches to the study of children's information seeking, traditionally an underpopulated area of research. Virginia Walter demonstrated that children's information needs are large and not limited to requests made to school librarians. Joanne Silverstein studied unconventional forms of information use, and Ciaran Trace studied informal information creation and use by children. Research on the "information behavior of a new generation" is discussed in the recent book edited by Beheshti and Large. During recent decades, a more sophisticated understanding has also developed of information genres and the ways they are shaped by practice.

Current trends

Information seeking in the digital age: With the proliferation of digital platforms, there is growing interest in how people search for, retrieve, and evaluate information across diverse online environments, such as social media, search engines, and specialized databases.

Social Media and Information Behavior: This is the growing area of research which focuses on how social media influences information diffusion and how individuals interact with information through different platforms, such as Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram. Research is mostly conducted around misinformation, echo chambers, and how algorithms affect exposure to information.

Personalized Information Systems: Research is also being conducted on how personalized information services (such as recommendation systems, AI-driven suggestions, etc.) affect information behavior. This includes issues such as privacy concerns, filter bubbles, and information overload.

Health Information Behavior: A very interesting area of study is how people search for health information, trust sources, and make health-related decisions, especially in the context of online health resources and telemedicine.

Information Literacy: The increased prevalence of misinformation and disinformation has

led to a renewed interest in improving information literacy, especially within the educational environment, to enhance how individuals evaluate the credibility of information.

User-Centered Design in Information Systems: Research is being conducted into better information systems design by determining how users interact with information, especially in complex contexts like academic databases, libraries, or enterprise systems.

Cross-Cultural and Contextual Studies: There is a growing need to understand how cultural, contextual, and societal factors influence information behavior, including language differences, socioeconomic factors, and global information inequality.

Conclusion

Understanding information research behavior is crucial in designing better information retrieval systems, improving education and research practices, and supporting decision-making in various sectors. By understanding the factors that influence how people search for, evaluate, and use information, researchers and organizations can create more user-centered tools, resources, and strategies that enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of information-seeking efforts.